

European network to promote grazing and to
support grazing-based farms on their
economic and ecologic performances as well
as
on animal welfare

Project Acronym: **Grazing4AgroEcology**

Project Number: 101059626

Deliverable No.: D2.2

Deliverable Title: List of indicators for self-assessment
as a result of task 2.2

Responsible Partner: Teagasc

Due date: 31 August 2023

Submission Date: 10 September 2023

Dissemination level: PU

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101059626	42 Months	September 2022

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101059626. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
C&D	Communication and dissemination
EIP	European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
FA	Facilitator Agents
G4AE	Grazing4AgroEcology
KIMS	Knowledge and Information Management System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MA	Multi Actor Approach
MS	Member States
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
OGs	Operational Groups
PF	Partner Farms
SO	Specific Objectives
SoMe	Social Media
STWG	Scientific Technical Working Group
WP	Work Package

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1 Objective

The main objective of the determination of indicators for assessing grazing capacities on farm level is to evaluate grazing farm performance through the five core principles of agroecology. The five principles of agroecology should be optimised to meet the challenges of economic, ecological and societal requirements as well as on animal welfare on farm. These principles have been divided into five pillars of agroecology and will be the core of the indicators for assessing grazing capacities at farm level.

Five pillars to be optimised in animal production systems:

1. adopting management practices that aim to improve animal health
2. reducing the inputs required for production
3. reducing pollution by optimising the biogeochemical functioning of farming systems
4. enhancing diversity within animal production systems to strengthen their resilience
5. preserving biodiversity in agro-ecosystems by adapting management practices

The indicators are supposed to be used within the G4AE self-assessment tool for assessing the grazing capacities on farm level as well as for benchmarking the optimization process according to the 5 principles of agroecology.

2 Determination of indicators assessing grazing capacity at farm level

2.1 Preparation of a mind map

A core team with internal experts centred around IDELE compiled a preliminary mind map to demonstrate the topics they believed important in France that link to the five pillars of agroecology. This gave them a basic understanding of the background required.

2.2 Interactive mentimeter workshop at the GPA meeting

To involve consortium members in the development of the list a mentimeter workshop was prepared for an interactive session as part of the WP2 presentation. Engagement from the consortium provided the opportunity to gain knowledge on what every MS deemed important as part of the five pillars of agroecology and the use of the mentimeter also highlighted any crossover or agreement/disagreement between MS. It also facilitated discussion on the pillars of agroecology amongst the consortium. Five questions directly associated to the five pillars of agroecology were asked.

1. What practices should be adopted to improve animal welfare?
2. How to best reduce the inputs required for production?
3. How to optimise the biogeochemical functioning of farms to reduce pollution?
4. How to enhance diversity within animal production systems to strengthen their resilience?
5. What practices should be adopted to preserve biodiversity in agroecosystems?

2.3 Further refinement of the of indicator list by the G4AE STWG

Responses from the consortium were compiled into excel by the STWG subgroup (IDELE and Teagasc) in the form of 'key words'. Feedback from the G4AE consortium was also received and included in excel. The responses were analysed and common EU terminology was applied to the excel spreadsheet. This streamlining of the spreadsheet gave a basis for the STWG sub group to begin dividing the excel spreadsheet methodically; key words were separated into the five pillars of agroecology (animal welfare, reduced inputs, reduced pollution, enhanced diversity and biodiversity; Appendix).

Key steps to compilation of list:

- Assigned into sub-pillars (i.e. health management as a sub-pillar of animal welfare).
- Every sub-pillar then was separated into categories (i.e. profilaxy as a category of health management)
- Indicators were finalised as questions with answers relative to on farm assessment (i.e. Health management: Do you implement a vaccination plan for all animals on farm? Yes/No)

Assigning of indicators was completed by the sub group using multiple sources (literature reviews, EU policy, subject specialists and farmer good practice from individual MS). The final list of indicators presented in the appendix was finalised as 140 indicators with some indicators represented in multiple pillars. The list of indicators in the appendix provide questions that assess grazing capacities at farm level and allow evaluation of farm performance through answers that provide information on the

indicators that are positively associated with management under the five pillars of agroecology (highlighted in green).

The sub group transferred these indicators be analysed by the STWG working group under each pillar for agroecology (1 group per pillar). Currently the STWG are working on feedback and weighting for the indicators selected for each pillar to be utilised across every MS as a self-assessment tool on farm. The selection indicators finalised for the self-assessment tool will be ready and presented to the consortium at the G4AE project meeting in Rennes in mid-September 2023.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059626.

3 Table of indicators

3.1 Final list of indicators.

Positive on farm indicator for each question is highlighted in green.

	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Indicator	
				Question	Value
1	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	Do you incorporate legumes in all grasslands?	Yes
					No
2	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	What is the average proportion of legumes in your grasslands in summer?	> 30%
					20-30%
					10-20%
					<10%
3	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Sufficient forage production	What percentage of forage used is produced on your farm?	100%
					> 70%
					< 70%
4	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Grassland Management	Is the target for post-mowing height is 6-8 cm for first cut silage?	Yes
					No
5	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Grassland Management	How many days on average do you spend grazing a year?	> 200 days
					150-200 days
					100 - 150 days
					< 100
6	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	Do you try to graze as early as possible in spring?	Yes
					No
7	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	When animals are grazing in the spring are they fed additional forage?	Yes
					No
8	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	If animals are given additional forage in	0 - 20%

				spring, what % of their diet is additional forage?	
					> 20%
9	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	During spring, how much concentrate do you feed a day?	0 kg/cow
					0 - 3 kg/cow
					>3kg
10	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	If you do feed concentrate in spring what crude protein percentage is it?	< 15%
					> 15%
11	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Summer grazing	During summer, how much of the day are animals grazing?	> 12 hours
					< 12 hours
					No grazing
12	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Summer grazing	During summer, how much concentrate do you feed a day?	0 kg
					1-3 kg
					>3 kg
13	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Autumn grazing	In autumn, how often do animals graze?	> 12 hours
					< 12 hours
					No grazing
14	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	What distance from your farm do concentrates come from?	Produced on farm
					<50 km from the farm
					50 - 200 km
					> 200 km
15	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	What percentage of forage is refused in the feed space?	< 10%
					> 10%
16	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	What percentage of dung and urine patches are left ungrazed in your paddock?	< 5%
					5-10%
					>10%
17	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	High quality forage	Do you mow early to cut high quality forage?	Yes
					No

18	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	High quality forage	Do you include legumes in your mown grasslands?	Yes
					No
19	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	What percentage of your farm has optimal soil fertility (mineral soils index 3/4 P and K and soil pH > 6.3)?	>90%
					70-90%
					<70%
20	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	Do you soil test your farm?	Yes
					No
21	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	What is the soil organic matter content of your permanent grasslands?	>3%
					<3%
22	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil health	Do you avoid soil compaction by avoiding grazing in very wet conditions, using low pressure tyres and limited use of heavy machinery?	All 3 options
					Only 2 options
					Just 1/0 options
23	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil health	Do you use minimum till methods for reseeding?	Yes
					No
24	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	Do you spread lime when required?	Yes
					No
25	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	Do you spread your manure and slurry on paddocks that produce forage and crops for your farm?	Yes
					No
26	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	Do you analyse your slurry and manure?	Yes
					No
27	Reducing inputs	Optimising chemical fertilisation	Precision technology	Do you use precision technology (i.e. GPS etc.) to spread chemical fertiliser?	Yes

					No
28	Reducing inputs	Optimising chemical fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	Do you consider nitrogen mineralisation across the year when spreading chemical fertiliser?	Yes
					No
29	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	Do you use low emission slurry and manure spreading to improve nitrogen content?	Yes
					No
30	Reducing inputs	Optimising chemical and organic fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	Do you match your nutrient application to plant growth?	Yes
					No
31	Reducing inputs	Optimising chemical fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	How much chemical nitrogen do you spread on your grazed grasslands?	<80 kg N/ha
					80 -150 kg N/ha
					150-200 kg N/ha
					> 200 kg N/ha
32	Reducing inputs	Optimising chemical fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	How much chemical nitrogen do you spread on your mown grasslands?	<100 kg N/ha
					100-200 kg N/ha
					>200 kg N/ha
33	Reducing inputs	Optimising chemical and organic fertilisation	Precision technology	Do you use a prediction tool to know when best to apply nutrients?	Yes
					No
34	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	How often do your mown grasslands get some organic matter (dung)?	Every 1 - 2 years
					3 or more years
35	Reducing pollution	Grassland management		Do you reseed your grasslands for tillage in autumn or late winter/early spring?	Late winter/early spring
					Autumn
36	Reducing pollution	Grassland management		Do you incorporate plantain in your swards?	Yes
					No

37	Reducing pollution	Grassland management		Do you maximise nutrient use to optimal soil fertility?	Yes
					No
38	Reducing pollution	Grazing management		Do you allocate the correct amount of herbage to avoid over or under grazing?	Yes
					No
39	Reducing pollution	Grazing management		Do you sacrifice a paddock to stock animals and offer extra forage/feed for more than a week?	Yes
					No
40	Reducing pollution	Grazing management		Do you feed high levels of concentrate (>3kg) with a high level of crude protein in spring (>15% crude protein) and in autumn (>16% crude protein)?	Yes
					No
41	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Infrastructures	Do you have adequate storage for manure and slurry?	Yes
					No
42	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Infrastructures	Does your slurry tank have a cover?	Yes
					No
43	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Material	Do you use a low emission slurry spreading to reduce nitrous oxide emissions?	Yes
					No
44	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Material	Do you have a flow meter to assess slurry applied?	Yes
					No
45	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Material	Do you use slurry additives?	Yes
					No
46	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Spreading	Do you adapt your spreading plan to the spreading risks associated with your soil types?	Yes
					No

47	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Spreading	Do you spread nutrient between February and September to match the application to plant growth?	Yes
					No
48	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Spreading	During reduced summer growth (i.e. drought), do you spread fertiliser?	Yes
					No
49	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	What percentage of bare ground do you have over winter on your farm?	0%
					1-5%
					6-10%
					>10%
50	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	Do you use a crop rotation plan if you have an area in tillage?	Yes
					No
51	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	Do you use legumes in your crop rotation if you have an area in tillage?	Yes
					No
52	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	Do you have cover crops that capture nitrogen if you have an area in tillage?	Yes
					No
53	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	What is the average duration of a crop rotation if you have an area in tillage?	≤ 3 years
					4-7 years
					≥ 8 years
54	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	Do you incorporate temporary grasslands for 3 years or more in your rotation if you have an area in tillage?	Yes
					No
55	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	What percentage of your farm is in permanent grassland?	> 70%
					50-70%
					30-49%
					<30%

56	Reducing pollution	Soil compaction	Soil cover	Do you avoid soil compaction by avoiding grazing in very wet conditions, using low pressure tires, limited use of heavy machinery?	3 options
					2 options
					1 or 0 option
57	Reducing pollution	Soil compaction	Soil cover	Do you use minimum till method for reseeding?	Yes
					No
58	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Pesticides use	Do you have a safe pesticide use training course completed?	Yes
					No
59	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Pesticides use	Do you spray when the weather conditions are favourable (dry, no wind)?	Yes
					No
60	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Biological control	Do you create habitat (hedgerows etc.,) for insects that will help for pest regulation?	Yes
					No
61	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Biological control	Do you correctly maintain your wetlands?	Yes
					No
62	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection		Do you fence all your waterways?	Yes
					No
63	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection		Do you include riparian margins next to waterways?	Yes
					No
64	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection		Do you respect a 5m boundary when spreading fertiliser/manure/slurry/pesticides near waterways?	Yes
					No
65	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection		Do you ensure no effluent escapes from your yard? (separate clean water pipes, pond, appropriate storage of silage)	Yes
					No

66	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection		Do you use a mapping tool for pollution potential?	Yes
					No
67	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	Do you choose species to graze as long as possible in your natural conditions?	Yes
					No
68	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	Do you try to incorporate multiple varieties in your seed mixture?	Yes
					No
69	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	Do you incorporate additional species to your grasslands (chicory, plantain, etc.)?	Yes
					No
70	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	Do you reduce your reliance on chemical fertiliser to the incorporation of legumes and to the utilisation of organic nutrients?	Yes
					No
71	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	Do you practice land exchanges with your neighbours to improve your grazing area?	Yes
					No
72	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	Do you have more than one grazing animal species for production?	Yes
					No
73	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	Do you practice first last stocking if you have more than one type of animal? (First last stocking: A method of utilizing two or more groups of animals, usually with different nutritional requirements, to graze sequentially on the same land area.)	Yes
					No

74	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	Do you practice creep grazing for young stock? (Creep grazing: A method of creep stocking where dams and offspring rotate through a series of paddocks with offspring as first grazers and dams as last grazers)	Yes
					No
75	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	Are your animal species adapted to your local conditions for grazing?	Yes
					No
76	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	How many breeds do you use for production (the breed must represent more than 10% of the animals of that species)	≥ 2 breeds
					1 breed
77	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	Do you implement cross breeding?	Yes
					No
78	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Fodder production	How many different types of forages/crops do you produce on your farm to maintain production over the year?	≥ 3 types
					2 types
					1 type
79	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Fodder production	Do you plant your forages at different time points?	Yes
					No
80	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Fodder production	Do you plant forages that can be harvested at different time points across the year?	Yes
					No
81	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Agroforestry	Do you incorporate agroforestry on your grasslands? (Agroforestry is a collective name for land-use systems and technologies where	Yes

				woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos, etc.) are deliberately used on the same land-management units as agricultural crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence.)	
					No
82	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of production	Agroforestry	How many woody species do you have?	≥ 6 species
					≤ 5 species
83	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of marketing	Quality labels	Do you have quality labels strongly linked to the territory (Protected Design of Origin)?	Yes
					No
84	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of marketing	Retailor network	How many different retailer networks do you have?	≥1
					1
85	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of marketing	Retailor network	Do you have the opportunity to change your retailer network easily?	Yes
					No
86	Enhancing diversity	Diversity of marketing	Retailor network	Do you directly sell your products?	Yes
					No
87	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Area in biodiversity	What percentage of your farm is a biodiversity area?	>10%
					10%
					5-9%
					<5%
88	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Linked habitats	Are your biodiverse areas well linked?	Linked to 2 other areas
					Linked to 1 other area
					Not linked
89	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	Choose the most representative plot of temporary grassland on your farm and do this calculation : Plot shape index for temporary grassland = perimeter / (2*(sqr(pi*surface)))	> 1.7

					1.1-1.7
					<1.1
90	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	Choose the most representative plot of permanent grassland on your farm and do this calculation: Plot shape index for temporary grassland = perimeter / (2*(sqr(pi*surface)))	> 1.7
					1.1-1.7
					<1.1
91	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	Choose the most representative plot of crops on your farm and do this calculation: Plot shape index for temporary grassland = perimeter / (2*(sqr(pi*surface)))	> 1.7
					1.1-1.7
					<1.1
92	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	How many plots are over 12 ha?	0
					1 - 2
					≥3
93	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Hedgerows	What proportion of your farm area has hedgerows?	>5%
					<5%
94	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Hedgerows	How many native woody species are incorporated in your hedgerow?	>10
					<10
95	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Hedgerows	Are the bottom of the hedgerows and tree lines left untouched?	Yes
					No
96	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Hedgerows	Is the hedge trimmed in winter or in spring/summer/autumn?	Winter
					Spring/summer/autumn
97	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Orchards	If you have an orchard, what is the density of trees in the orchard?	50-100 trees/ha
					>100 trees/ha

98	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Protection of natural areas	Do you have any SAC (special area of conservation) managed on your farm?	Yes
					No
99	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Riparian margins	Do you have native vegetation included in your riparian margin?	Yes
					No
100	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Nest boxes	Do you have nest boxes in your barns/sheds to shelter nocturnal birds?	Yes
					No
101	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Ponds/wetlands	Do you have ponds/wetlands on your farm?	Yes
					No
102	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Ponds/wetlands	Do you maintain ponds/wetlands on your farm?	Yes
					No
103	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Food supply for insects	Do you have flowering vegetation between February and October on your farm?	Yes
					No
104	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Control of invasive species	Do you control invasive species on your farm?	Yes
					No
105	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	Does your grassland contain an indicator species for biodiversity?	Yes
					No
106	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	How often do you mow your silage or hay fields beginning from the centre?	Always
					Sometimes
					Never
107	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	What percentage of your farm incorporates a rotation of practices (grazing, mowing) on the grasslands?	<50% of the surface with only one practice
					>50% of the surface with only one practice
108	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	Is mowing period tailored for ground nesting birds?	Yes

					No
109	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	Is there mowing of grazing refusals (urine/dung) patches?	Yes
					No
110	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	How much chemical nitrogen is applied to extensive grasslands?	<40 kg N/ha
					>40 kg N/ha
111	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Livestock management	Are livestock only treated with insecticide when needed?	Yes
					No
112	Animal Welfare	Infrastructures	Paths and roads quality	What is the average distance walked each day by the animals?	<1km
					1-1.5km
					>1.5km
113	Animal Welfare	Infrastructures	Paths and roads quality	What proportion of animals are lame each year?	<10%
					10-15%
					>15%
114	Animal Welfare	Infrastructures	Paths and roads quality	What width are your roadways?	≥4m
					3-4m
					<3m
115	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Paths and roads quality	Do your roadways have uneven surfaces?	No
					Yes
116	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Paths and roads quality	Are your roadways maintained yearly?	Yes
					No
117	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Access to shade/shelter	While at grazing, do animals have access to shade/ shelter?	Always
					Often
					Sometimes
					Never
118	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Housing	Are animals free to roam?	Yes
					No
119	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Housing	Do adult animals have access to cubicles (one cubicle per cow) or loose housing (4m ² /cow)?	Always
					Often

					Sometimes
					Never
120	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Housing	Is bedding comfortable, warm and free draining?	Yes
					No
121	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Water access and quality	Do animals have access to fresh clean water at all times (including grazing)?	Access to fresh clean water at all times
					Access to fresh water at all times
					Access to fresh water sometimes
					No access to water while grazing
122	Animal Welfare	Nutrition	Balanced ration	Do you manage diet transitions correctly?	Yes
					No
123	Animal Welfare	Nutrition	Balanced ration	Does the ration complement the forage quality?	Yes
					No
124	Animal Welfare	Nutrition	Forage quality	Do you have species with tannins (chicory, plantain, etc.)?	Yes
					No
125	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	Do you implement a vaccination plan for all animals on farm?	Yes
					No
126	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	Is your treatment of animals systematic or based on analyses (faeces and others?)	Analyses
					Systematic
127	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	How many times per year do you trim hooves?	≥ 1
					None
128	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	What is the frequency of mastitis?	≤ 1 / animal / year
					2 / animal / year
					≥ 3 / animal / year
129	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	What is the mortality rate in your replacement and adults animals?	$\leq 5\%$
					$> 5\%$

130	Animal Welfare	Health management	Veterinary services	Do you call the vet in a timely manner for sick animals?	Yes
					No
131	Animal Welfare	Health management	Veterinary services	How often do you check your animals?	2 times a day
					Daily
					Less than daily
132	Animal Welfare	Animal behaviour and welfare	Grazing management	How do you manage grazing?	Rotational: A method that utilizes recurring periods of grazing and rest among three or more paddocks in a grazing management unit throughout the time when grazing is allowed
					Continuous: A method of grazing livestock on a specific unit of land where animals have unrestricted and uninterrupted access throughout the time when grazing is allowed
133	Animal Welfare	Animal behaviour and welfare	Grazing management	Do you let your animals graze in unfavourably wet conditions?	Yes
					No
134	Animal Welfare	Animal behaviour and welfare	Freedom to express natural behaviour	Can the animals have social contacts between them?	Yes
					No
135	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	Is colostrum fed within 3 hours of birth?	Yes
					No
136	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	Is the colostrum of good quality? (>22% on the brix refractometer)	Yes
					No
137	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	Do calves share the same airspace as the older animals?	Yes
					No
138	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Freedom to express natural behaviour	How much space is allocated to calves?	≥2m ²
					1,5m ²
					<1,5 m

139	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Freedom to express natural behaviour	How long are calves kept on farm?	> 40 days
					≤ 40 days
140	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Freedom to express natural behaviour	Are calves housed individually?	Yes
					No

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